

Glycemic Control and Peripheral Arterial Disease in Patients with Diabetic Foot at General Hospital of Orizaba N.1

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Diabetic foot is one of the most serious complications associated with diabetes mellitus. Peripheral Arterial Disease (PAD) results from structural and functional alterations in the peripheral arteries. Poor glycemic control has been associated with accelerated PAD progression.

Objective: To evaluate the correlation between glycemic control and PAD in hospitalized patients with diabetic foot at the Orizaba Regional General Hospital No. 1.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted in 246 patients diagnosed with diabetic foot. Glycemic control was determined using glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), and PAD using the ankle-brachial index (ABI). Correlation tests (Spearman's rank correlation coefficient) and ROC analysis were applied to identify the optimal HbA1c cutoff point as a risk marker for PAD.

Results: The average age was 63 years, and the average duration of type 2 diabetes was 12 years. The mean HbA1c was 9.9%. Peripheral arterial disease (PAD) was identified in 88.6% of patients. A significant negative correlation was found between HbA1c and ankle-brachial index (ABI) ($p < 0.001$). Patients with PAD had higher HbA1c levels (10.13% vs. 7.83%). HbA1c (OR = 2.28) and smoking (OR = 10.1) were independently associated with PAD. ROC analysis showed an optimal HbA1c cutoff point of $\geq 8.6\%$ (AUC = 0.84).

Conclusions: Poor glycemic control is a factor in the development of PAD in patients with diabetic foot. An HbA1c $\geq 8.6\%$ represents a useful clinical threshold for identifying increased risk, highlighting the need for comprehensive metabolic control interventions

KEYWORDS: Peripheral arterial disease, diabetic foot, ankle-brachial index, San Elían classification, type 2 diabetes mellitus.

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is one of the world's leading public health problems and has been described as the pandemic of the 21st century due to its high prevalence, chronic nature, and impact on morbidity and mortality.¹ It is estimated that more than 500 million people currently live with this disease, and projections suggest continued growth in the

coming decades³. The long-term prognosis for patients with DM is determined by the development of chronic complications, both microvascular and macrovascular, which significantly compromise quality of life and survival.^{3,4}

Diabetic foot is one of the most serious chronic complications of DM. It is defined as a multifactorial

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clinical condition that includes infection, ulceration, and destruction of the deep tissues of the foot, generally associated with neuropathy and peripheral arterial disease (PAD). The latter represents a macrovascular manifestation of diabetes and is characterized by the progressive obstruction of the arteries in the lower limbs, leading to ischemia, delayed wound healing, recurrent infections, and, in advanced cases, the need for major amputations.³⁰

Insufficient glycemic control has been identified as a key factor in the pathophysiology of PAD. Chronic hyperglycemia induces oxidative stress, endothelial inflammation, and vascular dysfunction, mechanisms that favor the development and progression of atherosclerosis.²⁵ Several studies have shown that for every 1% increase in glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), the relative risk of developing PAD increases by 25 to 28%. This makes HbA1c not only a marker of metabolic control but also a clinical predictor of vascular complications.²⁶

In Mexico, diabetes mellitus is the leading cause of hospitalization and non-traumatic amputations, with a considerable impact on the healthcare system. Early identification of modifiable risk factors, such as glycemic control and smoking, is essential for designing prevention and treatment strategies that reduce vascular complications and preserve the affected limb.²⁹

In this context, studying the relationship between glycemic control and peripheral arterial disease (PAD) in patients with diabetic foot is of great clinical and epidemiological relevance. The aim is to provide evidence that will allow for the establishment of useful cut-off points in medical practice, optimize vascular risk stratification, and strengthen the comprehensive and multidisciplinary management of this population.³³

METHODS

Study Design

An observational, descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted to analyze the correlation between glycemic control and peripheral arterial disease in patients with diabetic foot at Regional Hospital No. 1 in Orizaba, Veracruz.

The research was conducted without deliberately manipulating the study variables, employing a non-experimental approach. Data were collected at a single point in time, with the aim of describing the study variables and analyzing their incidence and interrelationship at that specific moment.

Study Universe and Population

Patients diagnosed with diabetic foot admitted to the General Surgery and Angiology service during the period January 2023–January 2025.

Sample Selection

A non-probabilistic convenience sampling method was used, including all patients who met the established inclusion and

exclusion criteria and were treated during the study period (January 2023–January 2025).

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients covered by the Mexican Social Security Institute (IMSS).
- Patients hospitalized in General Surgery at HGRO1 with a diagnosis of diabetic foot.
- Age over 18 years.
- Patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus
- Patients who agreed to participate in the study after signing an informed consent form.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients without complete medical records
- Patients without a diagnosis of type 2 diabetes
- Patients with autoimmune diseases such as systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis, and vasculitis
- Patients who had undergone previous revascularization

Elimination Criteria

- Patients without valid health insurance coverage during the period January 2023–January 2025.

STUDY OVERVIEW

A cross-sectional, descriptive, observational study was initiated to analyze the correlation between glycemic control and peripheral arterial disease in patients with diabetic foot at Regional Hospital No. 1 in Orizaba, Veracruz. Patients diagnosed with diabetic foot who were hospitalized under the care of the General Surgery and Angiology services between January 2023 and January 2025 were identified. After obtaining informed consent, data collection began through doctor-patient interviews.

Patient identification information and study variables were recorded on a data collection sheet. These variables included age, sex, glycated hemoglobin levels, presence of comorbidities and substance use disorders, and ankle-brachial index (ABI). The ABI was measured using a Doppler ultrasound device, a transmitter gel, and a blood pressure cuff. With the patient in the supine position, systolic blood pressure was measured over the projection of the brachial artery at the elbow crease of both upper limbs. Subsequently, systolic blood pressure was measured over the projection of the dorsalis pedis and posterior tibial arteries of both lower limbs.

The ankle-brachial index (ABI) was calculated as the ratio of the highest value obtained in the posterior tibial and dorsalis pedis artery measurements to the highest systolic blood pressure in the arm. An ABI between 0.91 and 1.3 was considered normal. An ABI less than or equal to 0.9 was considered indicative of peripheral arterial disease (PAD), and an ABI above 1.3 was considered indicative of arterial calcification. For the purposes of this study, the San Elian classification was used to determine the severity of diabetic foot. Glycemic control was measured by measuring glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c). A result below 7% indicated controlled glycemia, while a result above 7% indicated

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uncontrolled glycemia. Fasting serum glucose at hospital admission was defined as a result below 180 mg/dL, considered controlled, and above 180 mg/dL, uncontrolled glycemia.

The results were entered into a database using Microsoft Excel, which was used for descriptive statistical analysis (frequency distribution, absolute and relative frequencies, and graphs). To assess the correlation between glycemic control and peripheral arterial disease (PAD) in patients with diabetic foot at Regional Hospital No. 1, Orizaba, the IBM SPSS statistical software was used to obtain Pearson's and Spearman's correlation coefficients to measure the degree of relationship between the two quantitative variables.

RESULTS

The study sample consisted of a total of 246 hospitalized patients diagnosed with diabetic foot in the angiology and general surgery service. The distribution by sex was 126 male patients (51.2%) versus 120 female patients (48.8%).

In the section on drug addictions and comorbidities present, 106 patients (43%) had a history of smoking and 110 patients (44.7%) had high blood pressure. Regarding glycemic control, HbA1c showed that only 5 (6.5%) of the patients were under good metabolic control (<7%), 8 (17.1%) patients presented mild control (7.1–8%), 24 (30.9%) patients moderate control (8.1–10%), and 71 (45.5%) patients had poor control categorized as severe (>10%).

171 (69.5%) of the patients presented glucose >200 mg/dl at the time of their hospital admission.

According to the severity classification, 84 (34.1%) patients had mild PAD, 110 (44.7%) patients had moderate PAD, and 24 (9.75%) patients had severe PAD. (Graph1).

Graph 1: Level peripheral arterial disease

Similarly, it was observed that patients with PAD have higher glycosylated hemoglobins, with an average HbA1c of 10.3% in the 110 (44.7%) patients with moderate PAD. (Graph 2).

Graph 2: Glycated hemoglobin according to PAD severity levels.

Regarding the severity level according to the San Elián classification for diabetic foot, 110 patients (44.7%) were mild, 106 patients (43%) were moderate, and 29 patients (11.7%) were severe.

HbA1c values averaged 9.9%, reinforcing the finding of poor glycemic control in most cases. Hospital stay averaged approximately 7 days, while the ankle-brachial index (ABI) showed pathological average values, consistent with the high prevalence of peripheral arterial disease (PAD) detected.

When evaluating the relationship between HbA1c and the ABI, a significant negative correlation was observed. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was -0.568 ($p < 0.001$), indicating that higher HbA1c levels were associated with lower ABI values, reflecting greater peripheral vascular compromise. Similarly, Pearson's correlation coefficient was also positive ($r = -0.578$, $p < 0.001$), further strengthening the finding and confirming the existence of a moderate-to-strong inverse association between poor glycemic control and vascular impairment. (Table 1)

Table 1: Spearman's correlation

Variable	Spearman rho	p-value
ABI	-0.568	0.0
Presence of PAD	0.37	0.0
Level of PAD	0.559	0.0
San Elián Score	0.563	0.0
Smoking	0.359	0.0

Furthermore, when analyzing the association between HbA1c categories and the presence of peripheral arterial disease using the chi-square test, a statistically significant difference was found ($\chi^2 = 40.37$; $p < 0.001$). Patients with higher HbA1c values presented with PAD more frequently than those with better metabolic control. (Table 2)

Table 2. Association between HbA1c and PAD using the chi-square test. Chi-square test: $\chi^2 = 40.37$, $p < 0.001$

HbA1c	No PAD	Yes EAP	Total	p-value
Good control (<7%)	8	8	16	
Mild (7.1–8%)	10	32	42	
Moderate (8.1–10%)	8	68	76	
Severe (>10%)	2	110	112	0.001
Total	28	218	246	

To determine the risk factors associated with peripheral arterial disease (PAD), a logistic regression model was performed that included glycated hemoglobin, age, sex, smoking, and hypertension as variables. The results showed that HbA1c remained a significant risk factor, with an odds ratio (OR) of 2.28 (95% CI: 1.52–3.43; $p < 0.001$), indicating that for every 1% increase in HbA1c values, the risk of developing PAD nearly doubles.

Smoking was also significantly associated with this complication, with an OR of 10.12 (95% CI: 1.09–93.7; $p < 0.05$), demonstrating that smokers have an approximately ten times greater risk of developing PAD compared to nonsmokers. In contrast, high blood pressure (OR = 3.90; 95% CI: 0.75–20.3), age (OR = 0.97; 95% CI: 0.93–1.01) and male sex (OR = 0.46; 95% CI: 0.18–1.19) did not reach statistical significance, although they showed trends that could be explored in studies with a larger sample size.

To evaluate the value of HbA1c in predicting peripheral arterial disease (PAD), a receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve was used. The area under the curve was 0.84, indicating adequate ability to differentiate between patients with and without PAD. To determine the optimal cutoff point for glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) as a predictor of PAD, the Youden index (J) was used, defined as $J = \text{Sensitivity} + \text{Specificity} - 1$. This index identifies the value that simultaneously maximizes the sensitivity and specificity of the test, ensuring the greatest discriminatory power between patients with and without PAD. According to this criterion, the selected cutoff point was $\text{HbA1c} \geq 8.6\%$, which achieved a sensitivity of 73% and a specificity of 82%. This suggests that HbA1c can be considered a useful marker not only for metabolic control but also for predicting peripheral vascular risk in patients with diabetic foot.

Table 3. ROC curve, which evaluates HbA1C the presence of PAD at different cohort points.

HbA1c Threshold	Sensitivity (TPR)	Specificity (FPR)	Optimal Cutoff Point
8.9	0.683	0.179	
8.8	0.702	0.179	
8.6	0.729	0.179	yes
8.5	0.748	0.214	
8.4	0.757	0.25	

DISCUSSION

In the sample of 246 hospitalized patients with diabetic foot, the median age was 63 years. This age is consistent with reports in the literature, where PAD is concentrated in older adults and its prevalence increases markedly with age, a phenomenon described in both population analyses and recent clinical practice guidelines. In particular, the 2024 ACC/AHA consensus documents underscore the strong age gradient of PAD and its clinical impact in advanced stages, reinforcing that the greatest disease burden is observed from the sixth decade of life onward.³²

Regarding sex in this study, the distribution was almost balanced: 126 (51%) men and 120 (49%) women. This corresponds to the findings of a 2022 study by Aday A et al., titled “Association between sex and race with the incidence of peripheral arterial disease among veterans with normal ankle-brachial indices.” That study reported that the risk of incident PAD was 50% lower in women than in men, but with disparities in major outcomes due to underdiagnosis, which may mask real differences in burden and severity. These findings help contextualize the sex distribution in our study and suggest that active diagnostic surveillance in women with diabetes and risk factors (smoking and hypertension) is clinically relevant.³³

These findings are consistent with those reported in the literature, where chronic hyperglycemia is recognized as a key determinant of macroangiopathic vascular damage. In our cohort, patients with PAD had an average HbA1c of 10.13%, significantly higher compared to patients without PAD (7.83%). Similarly, in the study by Bansal et al., entitled “Relationship between glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels and the duration of diabetes with peripheral arterial disease,” conducted in 100 patients, they found that HbA1c was significantly higher in diabetic patients with PAD (8.25%) compared to those without this complication (7.32%), confirming that even small differences in glycemic control can influence peripheral vascular risk.²⁷

The moderate-to-high negative correlation between HbA1c and ABI ($\rho = -0.568$, $p < 0.001$) coincides with that described by López-Suárez and colleagues in the study “Ankle-brachial index in patients with diabetes mellitus: prevalence and risk factors”, who reported that for every 1% increase in HbA1c there is a significant reduction in ABI values, reflecting progression of arterial obstruction.³¹

In the multivariate analysis, smoking was identified as an independent and significant risk factor for the presence of PAD, with an odds ratio close to 10. This result agrees with that reported by Goldman et al. in 2024, entitled “The relationship between cigarette smoking and peripheral arterial disease,” who demonstrated that smoking not only increases the incidence of critical ischemia, but also accelerates the progression to major amputations.²⁹

Regarding the discriminative capacity of HbA1c, the study population showed an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.84, with an optimal cutoff point of 8.6%. These results are

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comparable to those reported by Hobaus et al. in "Peripheral arterial disease and type 2 diabetes: Older patients still show improved survival thanks to glucose control." They found that HbA1c values above 8% are associated with a higher risk of major amputations in patients with diabetic foot (4). Similarly, Singh et al. documented that HbA1c \geq 9% is associated with an increased risk of macrovascular complications, including PAD.²⁵

On the other hand, the prevalence of PAD in this study population (88.6%) was higher than that reported in international studies, where it ranges between 30 and 60% in patients with diabetic foot.^{6,7} This difference could be explained by the fact that the population analyzed corresponds to a third-level referral hospital, which implies a concentration of more serious and advanced cases.

As described in the literature, chronic hyperglycemia induces endothelial dysfunction, oxidative stress, and inflammatory damage—processes that accelerate atherosclerosis in peripheral arteries. The findings in this research reinforce this pathophysiological model, as patients with higher HbA1c levels showed more severe vascular involvement.

Furthermore, the high prevalence of PAD in our sample (88.6%) exceeds that reported in some international studies, where it is estimated at between 30 and 60% in patients with diabetic foot¹. This could be due to the fact that our study population comes from a referral hospital, where more severe and complicated cases are typically treated, which is an important difference compared to population-based studies.

CONCLUSIONS

This research demonstrates a high prevalence of glycemic dysregulation and peripheral arterial disease (PAD) in hospitalized patients with diabetic foot, confirming the close relationship between impaired glucose metabolism and peripheral vascular deterioration. Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) acts not only as a marker of metabolic control but also as an independent risk factor for the development of PAD. In fact, it was shown that for every 1% increase in HbA1c values, the risk of developing this complication nearly doubled, and that values above 8.6% constitute a clinical alert threshold with adequate sensitivity and specificity for predicting arterial compromise.

Analysis of associations confirmed that patients with PAD had significantly higher HbA1c values compared to those without vascular involvement, and that there is a moderate-to-high negative correlation between HbA1c and the ankle-brachial index (ABI). These findings are consistent with those reported in the international literature and reinforce the role of chronic hyperglycemia as a trigger for atherosclerotic processes and peripheral ischemia. Furthermore, smoking was identified as a key risk factor, increasing the probability of peripheral artery disease (PAD)

up to tenfold, which underscores the importance of addressing it in preventive strategies.

These results provide solid evidence for the need to implement strict and sustained glycemic control programs in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and diabetic foot, along with comprehensive interventions that include smoking cessation and the management of cardiovascular comorbidities. The identification of an HbA1c cutoff point with predictive value for PAD offers a practical tool for risk stratification and the design of early vascular surveillance protocols.

Finally, this work highlights the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to managing diabetic foot, where metabolic control, prevention of risk factors, and timely detection of vascular complications are fundamental pillars for reducing the risk of amputations and improving patients' quality of life. Likewise, identifying these patients in the general surgery service allows for timely referral to the angiology and vascular surgery service, where, in addition to identifying the severity of the disease with more specific studies, surgical interventions such as revascularization can be implemented, reducing the morbidity and mortality associated with radical treatments such as supracondylar amputations.

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